

On Helicopter View and Quality Research

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Abstract: Hamza Hamadah was supervised by Nina Thornhill at Imperial College from 2015 to 2017. Hamza's research focused on data-driven models for optimization of parallel electric compressor systems. This is a note of thank you.

Keywords: Postgraduate studies, Imperial College, supervisor, data-driven models, compressor systems.

It was an honor for me to be supervised by Prof. Nina Thornhill during my postgraduate studies at Imperial College London back in 2015-2017. I have completed MSc dissertation under her supervision and as part of her research group in the area of Data-Driven models for optimization of parallel electric compressor systems. It was a rich and enjoyable journey.

Having had few years of experience with Saudi Aramco before working under her supervision allowed me to build practical insight into the field of process control. Yet, the year I spent working with her was precious and career-defining as I was privileged to have direct insight representing years of cumulative experience as well as state-of-the-art theoretical developments in the fields of process monitoring and control.

It goes without saying that Prof. Thornhill has enriched the process systems engineering body of knowledge with her contributions over the years. By and large, I believe what uniquely defined her contributions is the well-balanced research orientation between theory and practice, and her agile approach in addressing industry problems through data-driven research techniques, both of which are appreciated by working professionals like myself. In retrospect, I like to say

that she kept the "helmet" in front of her eyes, signifying how her work directly touches industry's pain areas.

She taught me a lot. She inspired me and kept me passionate not only about working with data, but also about researching and exploring literature. Among many things, I learned the basic skills of defining research problems as well as cross-examining and navigating through published work through "helicopter view". Furthermore, she taught me how to remain focused, structured, and organized. What intrigued me more about her is that she always put the inspiration and guidance of young researches as key priority, despite her busy schedule.

In addition, she consistently emphasized the importance of "quality" in research, and the word of "predatory publishers" remains in my mind as a highlight after working with her. I have known Prof. Thornhill as personable, humble, and inspiring person. She is leaving the community with rich legacy behind her, not only in terms of published work, but also whole generations of inspired academicians and professionals.

A final word to Nina: This is a chance for me to say Thank You. I wish you the best in the next chapter of your life.